

Spectrophotometric Investigation of Some Colourless Complexes of Beryllium(II)

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CHROMEAZUROL S (CAS) is one of the many chromogenic reagents¹ used for the estimation of trace quantities of beryllium. Most of these reagents give colour reaction only in the alkaline region where the nature of the free beryllium species becomes doubtful and this makes reliable quantitative measurements of the metal-dye equilibrium system difficult. We have previously studied a number of colourless complexes of beryllium with oxygen donor ligands by a potentiometric titration technique². It was of interest to see whether any such ligand would serve as a suitable reagent for a photometric titration of beryllium using CAS as an indicator. The Be²⁺-CAS reaction takes place in a suitable pH range and has been previously studied by a number of workers³⁻⁶. The present note describes the effect of malonic acid, chromotropic acid, tiron, sodium fluoride and sodium pyrophosphate on the metal dye system. The composition and the equilibrium constants for the bleaching reaction have been computed by a suitable spectrophotometric method. Preliminary work on the use of pyrophosphate ion in a static photometric titration has also been described.

Experimental

Chromeazurol S (Fluka) was purified by double recrystallisation as free acid. Beryllium solution was prepared from BeSO₄·4 H₂O (E. Merck GR) and standardised gravimetrically. All other reagents were AR or equivalent grade. Spectrophotometric measurements were made on a Beckman DU spectrophotometer using 1.00 cm cells. For bleaching experiments, colour was developed with excess CAS at pH 5.2 using hexamine buffer, in presence of gum arabic as a stabiliser and EDTA as masking agent for any trace impurities. Absorbance values were measured after 1 hr. The molar extinction coefficient of the complex and reagent under these conditions were found to be 2.3 × 10⁴ and 3 × 10³ respectively at 570 nm.

Results and Discussion

CAS, because of its dual coordinating sites can form both 1:1 and 2:1 (metal:dye) complexes with the beryllium ion. It has however been shown⁷ that concentration of Be²⁺ lower than 10⁻³ M leads to the formation of a 1:1 complex only. The bleaching reactions with different ligands can then be represented as BeR + nL ⇌ BeL_n + R where R is CAS, L the bleaching ligand and n, the number of these ligands getting attached to Be²⁺. So that

$$\bar{K} = \frac{(\text{BeL}_n)(\text{R})}{(\text{BeR})(\text{L})^n} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

All along the spectrum, the absorbance of the BeR + L systems lies between those for BeR and R, thus ruling out the possibility of mixed ligand chelate formation. Now if x is the concentration of the colourless BeL_n formed, then the observed optical density (measured against water) will be given by

$$A = \epsilon_1 \frac{[(\text{BeR}) - x]}{\text{Total}} + \epsilon_2 \frac{[(\text{R}) + x]}{\text{Total}} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are the molar extinction coefficients of BeR and R respectively. x calculated from equation (2) can be used to calculate \bar{K} according to eq.

$$\bar{K} = \frac{[x][\text{R} + x]}{[(\text{BeR}) - x][(\text{L}) - nx]^n} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

\bar{K} can be calculated for n=1 or 2. That value of n leading to constancy of \bar{K} is taken as the true value for the composition of the colourless complex formed. A set of concordant \bar{K} values for a given stoichiometry

TABLE 1

Concentration of chromotropic acid	log $\bar{K}(\text{BeL})$	log $\bar{K}(\text{BeL}_2)$	Composition
9.992 × 10 ⁻⁶ M	0.49	5.75	
2.498 × 10 ⁻⁵ M	0.46	5.25	1:1
7.494 × 10 ⁻⁵ M	0.46	4.69	
1.4988 × 10 ⁻⁴ M	0.47	4.37	

are shown in Table 1. Of the bleaching agents, pyrophosphate ion with a favourable 1:1 stoichiometry was found to be the most promising photometric titrant (Table 2).

TABLE 2

Ligand	Composition	Log \bar{K}
Malonic acid	1:2	4.78
Fluoride	1:2	4.41
Chromotropic acid	1:1	0.47
Tiron	1:1	-1.90
Pyrophosphate	1:1	1.90

A static titration using CAS as indicator is depicted in Fig 1.

Fig. 1. Photometric titration of Be²⁺
Be²⁺ = 2.0 mg, CAS = 0.500 mg,
pH = 4.0, λ = 570 nm, total volume = 50 ml
Be²⁺ found = 2.0 mg.

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Estimation of *p*-Benzoquinone with Titanium(III) Chloride

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KNECHT and Hibbert¹ estimated quinone with titanium(III) chloride using methylene blue as indicator. They had taken the aqueous solution of benzoquinone to which added a very dilute methylene blue solution and titrated with titanium(III) chloride till methylene blue was decolourised. Incidentally we have found that the results were 1.5-2.0% high because of the slow reaction between the indicator and titanium (III). So in the light of which we have studied the reaction in detail and the methods for the accurate determination of quinone using some more indicators are given.

Experimental

About 0.06*N* *p*-benzoquinone solution is prepared and standardised iodometrically², 0.1 *N* titanium(III) chloride in 2.0 *N* HCl. standardised with potassium dichromate³, 0.2% aqueous cacotheline solution and 0.1% aqueous solutions of methylene blue, thionine, variamine blue, neutral red, phenosafranine and safranine-T are used.

Procedure: An aliquot volume of quinone is taken in the titration vessel which is fitted with a three holed rubber stopper, one hole accommodates the tip of the microburette, through the other two holes pass the inlet and outlet tubes for carbon dioxide. Then required volume of 1 : 1 HCl. or 1 : 3 H₂SO₄ is added to the titration vessel in the case of all indicators, so that the overall acid concentration is 1.0 *N* in a total volume of 40 ml. 0.3 ml. of cacotheline or 0.05 ml. of other indicators are added in each case and the required amount of oxalic acid is added so that the overall oxalic acid concentration is 0.01 *M* in the case of methylene blue, cacotheline and thionine and 0.10 *M* in the case of variamine blue, neutral red, phenosafranine and safranine-T. Carbon dioxide is passed through the contents for 10 min. The titration is then carried out with titanium(III) chloride solution to the appearance of pink colour in the case of cacotheline and to the disappearance of the dye colour in all other cases. In the case of variamine blue 0.3 ml. of indicator should

TABLE 1—ESTIMATION OF QUINONE WITH TiCl₃ IN *N* HCl AND 1 *N* H₂SO₄.

Indicator	1 <i>N</i> HCl medium	
	taken	found
Methylene blue.	4.342 39.08	4.349 39.10
Cacotheline.	6.513 39.10	6.518 39.12
Thionine.	4.103 36.72	4.111 36.67
Variamine blue.	3.129 27.63	3.132 27.52
Neutral red.	3.068 28.22	3.064 28.31
Phenosafranine.	3.068 27.61	3.060 27.70
Safranine-T	4.400 27.65	4.412 27.74
	1 <i>N</i> H ₂ SO ₄ medium	
Methylene blue.	4.342 39.08	4.345 39.12
Cacotheline.	6.513 39.10	6.518 39.14
Thionine.	6.154 28.72	6.150 28.63
Variamine blue.	3.375 28.29	3.380 28.39
Neutral red.	3.313 27.61	3.323 27.50
Phenosafranine.	3.405 27.64	3.412 27.72
Safranine-T.	5.281 39.60	5.291 39.50